

Copper(II) complexes with a (N,O)-donor Schiff base ligand : Syntheses, crystal structure, DNA interaction study and molecular docking

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Manuscript received online 02 January 2014, revised 14 August 2014, accepted 24 August 2014

Abstract : Syntheses and structural characterization of two copper(II) complexes, [Cu(L)] (1) and [Cu₂(L)(NCS)(H₂O)₂] (2) [L = *N,N'*-bis(salicylaldehyde)-1,3-diaminopropan-2-ol] have been reported. The structure of 1 has been determined by single crystal X-ray diffraction study while spectroscopic characterization has been performed to determine the structure for 2. Complex 1 crystallizes in *P*-1 space group with *a* = 7.7816(10) Å, *b* = 9.5871(12) Å and *c* = 10.5879 Å. Electron paramagnetic resonance (EPR) spectra of the copper(II) complexes 1 and 2 show a broad signal at *g* = 2.07 and 2.11. The binding property of the complexes with calf thymus DNA (CT-DNA) has been investigated using absorption and emission studies, viscosity experiments and cyclic voltammetry studies. Spectroscopic and hydrodynamic investigations revealed an intercalative mode of binding of 1 and 2 with CT-DNA. The copper(II) complexes have been found to induce effective cleavage of the supercoiled pBR 322 DNA. Molecular docking reveals that the complex 1 interacts with CT-DNA through substantial hydrogen bonding.

Keywords : Copper(II), Schiff base, crystal structure, EPR spectroscopy, DNA binding, DNA cleavage.

Introduction

The interaction between transition metal complexes with DNA has long been the subject of intense investigation for the development of new probes as agents for mediation of strand scission of duplex DNA and as chemotherapeutic agents for biotechnology and medicine¹⁻³. Studies of transition metal complexes, which react at specific sites along a DNA strand, provide routes toward rational drug design and have shown significant promise as diagnostic probes, reactive agents and therapeutics⁴⁻⁶. Metal complexes are known to bind to DNA via both covalent and non-covalent interactions. In covalent binding the labile ligand of the complexes is replaced by a nitrogen base of DNA such as guanine N7. In fact, cisplatin, an important antitumor drug is thought to bind to DNA through an intrastrand crosslink between neighbouring guanine residues created by covalent binding to two soft purine nitrogen atoms⁷. On the other hand,

the non-covalent DNA interactions include intercalative, electrostatic and groove (surface) binding of metal complexes along outside of DNA helix, along major or minor groove⁸⁻¹⁰. Considerable useful applications of these complexes need to be done to develop the metal complexes binding to DNA through an intercalation mode with the ligands containing fully planar intercalating into the adjacent base pairs of DNA¹¹. The intercalating ability not only correlates to the planarity of ligand, but also relates with the coordination geometry of the metal ion and donor atom type of the ligand¹¹. In addition, both the metal ion type and its valence play important roles in deciding the binding extent of complexes to DNA¹². This gives valuable information to explore the potential chemotherapeutic agents. Lots of octahedral copper(II) complexes have been synthesized and their interactions with DNA studied extensively¹³, where as relatively few studies on square planar Cu^{II} complexes have been reported to date.

In this present study, we have synthesized a mononuclear square planar Cu^{II} complex and a binuclear square pyramidal Cu^{II} complex with a (N,O)-donor Schiff base ligand [L = *N,N'*-bis(salicylaldehyde)-1,3-diaminopropan-2-ol] to react with metal salts and bridging ligand. The Cu^{II} complexes effectively take part into CT-DNA binding and pBR 322 DNA cleavage activity. Molecular docking reveals that the complex **1** interacts with DNA through substantial hydrogen bonding.

Results and discussion

Synthesis and solution properties of the Cu^{II} complexes :

The Schiff base ligand (L), *N,N'*-bis(salicylaldehyde)-1,3-diaminopropan-2-ol was synthesized by condensing 1,3-diaminopropan-2-ol with 2-salicylaldehyde in 1 : 2 molar ratio in dry ethanol. The ligand was characterized by IR, UV-Vis and ¹H NMR spectral analysis. The complex **1** was prepared by treating copper(II) chloride dihydrate with the Schiff base ligand in equimolar quantities in methanol as solvent. The dinuclear copper(II) complex **2** was prepared by treating copper(II) chloride dihydrate with the Schiff base ligand and ammonium thiocyanate in 2 : 1 : 1 molar quantities using methanol as solvent. The complexes **1** and **2** have been isolated as green colour crystals and brown coloured crystalline compound respectively. Based on elemental analysis the complexes **1** and **2** were formulated as [Cu(L)] and [Cu₂(L)(NCS)(H₂O)₂], and the stoichiometries of **1** and **2** were confirmed by single crystal X-ray structure determination along with different spectroscopic tools. The complexes are moderately soluble in common organic solvents such as MeOH, MeCN and DMSO. They are stable in the solid state as well as in the solution phase. The electronic absorption spectra of the **1** and **2** complexes in methanol solution are very similar to each other and show a broad low energy ligand field (LF) band in the visible region 603–615 nm. The intense absorption bands observed in the UV region (233–271 nm) is attributed to the intraligand $\pi \rightarrow \pi^*$ transition in the coordinated imines of the ligand origin. The low intensity bands (325–370 nm), which is assignable to phenolate anion to Cu^{II} ligand to metal charge transfer (LMCT) transition, reveals the involvement of the phenolate oxygen atom in coordination even in solution. In order to probe the solution stability of the complexes, we have performed UV-Vis spectral measurements for methanolic

solution of the complexes at room temperature at various time intervals. The LF band in the visible region (603–615 nm) of all the complexes remained unaffected over a period of at least 3 days revealing that the complexes are stable in solution at room temperature.

Spectroscopic characterization :

IR spectrum of the free ligand is characterized mainly by the strong peaks at 3412 and 1636, 1611 cm⁻¹ which are attributed to the stretching frequencies of -OH (aromatic) and C=N (imine) respectively. In IR spectrum of **1** the well resolved peak at 3202 cm⁻¹ is attributed to aliphatic ν (O-H) and the peaks at 1627, 1601 cm⁻¹ are due to ν (C=N) (Fig. S1)¹⁴. In IR spectrum of **2** the well resolved peak at 2079 cm⁻¹ is attributed to aliphatic ν (NCS) and the peaks at 1625, 1603 cm⁻¹ are due to ν (C=N) (Fig. S1). The presence of strong peak at 852 cm⁻¹ assigns the alkoxo-bridge between metal centers¹⁴. The compound shows weak bands in the range 2980–2900 cm⁻¹ are assignable to the aliphatic C-H stretching frequency.

The mass spectral studies of Cu^{II} complexes in acetonitrile are in good agreement with the theoretical molecular mass of the complexes and also the data confirm the mononuclear and dinuclear nature of the Cu^{II} complexes **1** and **2** respectively. The ESI mass spectra (Figs. S2 and S3) of **1** and **2** show molecular ion peaks at 359.16 (calcd. 359.86) and 516.08 (calcd. 516.58) respectively. ESI-MS (MeCN) *m/z* 359.16 [CuL+H]⁺ (calcd. 359.86), 516.08 [[Cu₂L(NCS)(H₂O)₂]+H]⁺ (calcd. 516.58).

X-Ray structure :

The crystal structure of **1** was reported and briefly described previously by Katajima *et al.*^{19b}. X-Ray single crystal diffraction reveals that the compound **1** crystallizes in triclinic *P*-1 space group and the asymmetric unit contains one Cu atom and a ligand. The complex has a twisted square-planar structure with *cis*-orientation of the ligands where the Cu^{II} co-ordinates with two imine nitrogens (N1, N2) atoms and two phenolate oxygens (O1, O2) atoms (Fig. 1). The structure is distinctly distorted from planarity; the dihedral angle between the O₁Cu₁N₁ and O₂Cu₁N₂ is 35.9°. The distortion of the planarity may be due to the isopropyl group connected with two N atoms which associates the steric congestion. The hydroxyl group of isopropanol forms hydrogen bond

Fig. S1. IR spectra of ligand (black) and Cu^{II} complexes (blue).

Fig. S2. Mass spectrum of [Cu(L)] (**1**) in acetonitrile medium.

with co-ordinated O atom using (O3–H3···O2; $d/\text{Å}$, $\theta/^\circ$: 1.742 Å, 154.33°, Table S1) make a 1D chain (Fig. 3). The complex has interlocked packing (Fig. S4) and it is stabilized by weak van der Waal interactions. A summary of the crystallographic data and structure refine-

ment parameters is given in Table 1. The bond angle and bond distance data are given in Table 2 for **1**. We cannot produce suitable crystals of **2** for single crystal X-ray diffraction study and hence we perform different spectroscopic analysis to proposed the 2D molecular geometry,

Fig. S3. Mass spectrum of $[\text{Cu}_2(\text{L})(\text{NCS})(\text{H}_2\text{O})_2]$ (2) in acetonitrile medium.

Fig. 1. An ORTEP diagram of **1** with 30% ellipsoid probability.

Table S1. Hydrogen bonds (Å)

D-H...A	D...H (Å)	H...A (Å)	D...A (Å)	D-H...A (deg)
O3-H3...O2	1.0400	1.7400	2.7242	155.00
C9-H9...O1	0.9800	2.5500	3.3704	142.00

which suggests that the ligand behaves as dinucleating compartment consisting of two Cu^{II} ions in a square pyramidal geometry (Fig. 2).

Fig. 2. Molecular geometry of the complex **2**.

Fig. 3. 1D chain of the complex **1**.

Electron Paramagnetic Resonance (EPR) studies :

EPR spectra of the complexes are recorded at liquid nitrogen temperature (LNT). The solid-state EPR spec-

Fig. S4. Interlocked structure of the complex **1**.

Table 1. Crystal data and structure refinement parameters for **1**

Empirical formula	C ₁₇ H ₁₆ N ₂ O ₃ Cu
Formula weight	359.86
Temperature	150 K
Wavelength	0.71073 Å
Crystal system	Triclinic
Space group	<i>P</i> -1
Unit cell dimensions	<i>a</i> = 7.7816(10) Å; <i>α</i> = 92.234(3)° <i>b</i> = 9.5871(12) Å; <i>β</i> = 104.920(3)° <i>c</i> = 10.5879(13) Å; <i>γ</i> = 95.976(3)°
Volume	757.33(16) Å ³
<i>Z</i>	2
Density (calculated) (mg/m ³)	1.578
Absorption coefficient (mm ⁻¹)	1.458
<i>F</i> (000)	370
Crystal size (mm ³)	0.38 × 0.76 × 1.00
Theta range for data collection	2.73 to 25.02°
Index ranges	-9 ≤ <i>h</i> ≤ 9, -11 ≤ <i>k</i> ≤ 11, -10 ≤ <i>l</i> ≤ 12
Reflections collected	10349
Independent reflections	2636 [<i>R</i> (int) = 0.030]
Completeness to theta = 28.33°	99.4%
<i>T</i> _{max} and <i>T</i> _{min}	0.577 and 0.216
Goodness-of-fit on <i>F</i> ²	0.998
Final <i>R</i> indices [<i>I</i> > 2σ(<i>I</i>)]	<i>R</i> 1 = 0.0316, <i>wR</i> 2 = 0.1119
<i>R</i> indices (all data)	<i>R</i> 1 = 0.0340, <i>wR</i> 2 = 0.1141
Largest diff. peak and hole (e.Å ⁻³)	1.49 and -0.34

Table 2. Bond lengths [Å] and angles [°] for **1**

Bond distances			
Cu(1)-N(1)	1.935(2)	Cu(1)-O(1)	1.9024(18)
Cu(1)-N(2)	1.948(2)	Cu(1)-O(2)	1.8986(18)
Bond angles			
O(1)-Cu(1)-O(2)	91.67(7)	O(2)-Cu(1)-N(2)	94.63(8)
O(1)-Cu(1)-N(1)	93.98(8)	N(1)-Cu(1)-N(2)	91.43(9)
O(1)-Cu(1)-N(2)	153.32(8)	O(2)-Cu(1)-N(1)	154.45(8)

trum of the mononuclear copper(II) complex **1** shows four lines with nuclear hyperfine spin 3/2 due to hyperfine splitting. For the mononuclear Cu^{II} complex **1**, the observed *g*_∥, *g*_⊥ and *A*_∥ values are 2.21, 2.07 and 177 respectively. Broad spectrum centered at *g* = 2.11 is observed for the dinuclear copper(II) complex due to an antiferromagnetic interaction between the two copper ions. Fig. 4 shows the EPR spectra of the mono- and binuclear copper(II) complexes **1** and **2**. The observed EPR spectral values are similar to reported mono- and dinuclear Cu^{II} complexes¹⁵.

Fig. 4. X-band EPR spectrum of the Cu^{II} complexes **1** and **2** at 77 K.

DNA binding investigation with Cu^{II} complexes :

Spectrophotometric titration :

The interaction of the Cu^{II} complexes with CT-DNA has been investigated by using spectrophotometric titration. Monitoring the changes in absorption spectrum of the metal complexes upon addition of increasing amounts of DNA is one of the most widely used methods for determining overall binding constants. The DNA binding experiments were performed in Tris-HCl buffer (50 mM

Tris-HCl, pH 8) using a Tris base solution of the complexes **1** and **2**. The concentration of DNA was determined from the absorption intensity at 260 nm with an ϵ value¹⁶ of $6600 \text{ M}^{-1} \text{ cm}^{-1}$. Absorption titration experiments were made using different concentrations of DNA, while keeping the complex concentration constant. Due correction was made for the absorbance of the DNA itself. Samples were equilibrated before recording each spectrum. Hyperchromic and hypochromic effect are the spectral features of DNA concerning its double-helix structure. Broad spectra in the range 250–450 nm for **1** and 250–350 nm for **2** are shown in the UV-Vis spectrum of the respective complexes. Upon addition of calf-thymus DNA to **1** and **2**, it is clearly observed that the absorption peaks at 278 and 270 nm undergoes a significant decrease in molecular absorption (Figs. 5 and 6) (hypochromic effect) with no detectable shift in the absorption

wavelength. In case of intercalation, the complex undergoes bathochromism as the π^* orbital of the intercalated ligand couple with the π orbital of the DNA base pairs, hence lowering the π - π^* transition energy¹⁶. In our case, the possibility of a strong interaction with CT-DNA is considered and it is more in keeping with the intercalation binding mode¹⁶. The binding constants, K_b for the complexes **1** and **2** have been determined from the plot of $[\text{DNA}]/(\epsilon_A - \epsilon_F)$ vs $[\text{DNA}]$ and found to be 2.73×10^4 ($R = 0.996$ for five points) and 2.32×10^4 ($R = 0.99$ for five points) (Figs. 5 and 6).

Spectrofluorimetric titration :

Ethidium bromide (EB) has been used to probe the interaction of a complex with DNA. To evaluate the interaction mode of the complexes **1** and **2**, EB fluorescence intensity quenching experiments were done. In fact the EB fluorescence intensity will be enhanced in the

Fig. 5. Changes in the electronic absorption spectra of **1** ($50 \mu\text{M}$) with increasing concentrations (0 – $25 \mu\text{M}$) of CT-DNA; the increase of DNA concentration is indicated by an arrow. Plot of $[\text{DNA}]/(\epsilon_A - \epsilon_F)$ vs $[\text{DNA}]$ for the titration of CT-DNA with **1** in Tris-HCl buffer, binding constant $K_b = 2.73 \times 10^4 \text{ M}^{-1}$ ($R = 0.996$ for five points).

Fig. 6. Changes in the electronic absorption spectra of **2** ($50 \mu\text{M}$) with increasing concentrations (0 – $25 \mu\text{M}$) of CT-DNA; the increase of DNA concentration is indicated by an arrow. Plot of $[\text{DNA}]/(\epsilon_A - \epsilon_F)$ vs $[\text{DNA}]$ for the titration of CT-DNA with **2** in Tris-HCl buffer, binding constant $K_b = 2.32 \times 10^4 \text{ M}^{-1}$ ($R = 0.99$ for five points).

presence of DNA because of its intercalation into the helix, and it is quenched by the addition of another molecule that displaces EB from DNA¹⁷. Here, a significant decrease of the fluorescence intensity of EB bound to DNA was recorded by increasing the concentration of both complexes (Figs. 7 and 8). This observation of EB fluorescence quenching leads us to deduce that the copper(II) complexes may interact with DNA through the

plex] the concentration of the quencher. From the slope of the regression line in the derived plot of I_0/I versus [complex] (Figs. 7 and 8), the K_{sv} values for **1** and **2** were found to be 2.67×10^4 ; ($R = 0.97$ for five points) and 1.83×10^4 ; ($R = 0.90$ for five points), indicating a strong affinity of the complex to CT-DNA.

Hydrodynamic studies :

To further probe and distinguish between a groove

Fig. 7. Emission spectra of the CT-DNA-EB system in Tris-HCl buffer based on the titration of **1**. $k_{ex} = 522$ nm; the arrow indicates the increase of the complex concentration. Plot of I_0/I vs [complex] for the titration of CT-DNA-EB system with **1** using spectrofluorimeter; linear Stern-Volmer quenching constant (K_{sv}) for **1** = 2.67×10^4 ($R = 0.97$ for five points).

Fig. 8. Emission spectra of the CT-DNA-EB system in Tris-HCl buffer based on the titration of **2**. $k_{ex} = 522$ nm; the arrow indicates the increase of the complex concentration. Plot of I_0/I vs [complex] for the titration of CT-DNA-EB system with **2** using spectrofluorimeter; linear Stern-Volmer quenching constant (K_{sv}) for **2** = 1.83×10^4 ($R = 0.90$ for five points).

intercalation binding mode, releasing some EB molecules from the EB-DNA system¹⁸. The quenching of EB bound to DNA by the copper(II) complex is in agreement with the linear Stern-Volmer equation :

$$I_0/I = 1 + K_{sv} [\text{complex}]$$

where I_0 and I represent the fluorescence intensities in the absence and presence of quencher, respectively. K_{sv} is the linear Stern-Volmer quenching constant and [com-

plex] the concentration of the quencher. From the slope of the regression line in the derived plot of I_0/I versus [complex] (Figs. 7 and 8), the K_{sv} values for **1** and **2** were found to be 2.67×10^4 ; ($R = 0.97$ for five points) and 1.83×10^4 ; ($R = 0.90$ for five points), indicating a strong affinity of the complex to CT-DNA.

binding, intercalative or partial intercalative and groove binding modes, viscosity of the DNA solution was measured in presence of increasing concentrations of **1** and **2** and the change in relative viscosities with varying inputs of **1** and **2** were estimated¹⁹. Hydrodynamic method provides unequivocal evidence for the mode of binding¹⁹. The relative specific viscosity of the CT-DNA-**1** and CT-DNA-**2** complexes increased steadily as the D/P (com-

plex/DNA molar ratio) increased and ultimately attained saturation at $D/P \geq 0.5$ and $D/P \geq 0.6$ respectively (Fig. 9). The results favour a intercalation mode of binding of the copper(II) complexes into the double helical organization of the CT-DNA.

Fig. 9. Plot of η'_{sp}/η_{sp} versus D/P [DNA/1 (●), DNA/2 (■)].

Cyclic voltammetry :

The application of the cyclic voltammetric technique to the study of interaction between the metal complexes and DNA provides a useful complement to the previously used spectral studies²⁰. The electrochemical studies of Cu^{II} complexes **1** and **2** alone and upon addition of CT-DNA were performed in Tris buffer medium and the result is shown in Fig. 10. The mononuclear Cu^{II} complex **1** show one quasi-reversible reduction wave ($E_{pc}^1 = -0.99$ V and $E_{pa}^1 = -0.77$ V) in the cathodic potential at $E_{1/2} = -0.88$ V versus Ag/AgCl. The dinuclear Cu^{II} complex **2** is associated with two quasi-reversible reduc-

tion waves. The first and second reduction potentials for the dinuclear Cu^{II} complex **2** is observed at $E_{pc}^1 = -0.34$ and $E_{pc}^2 = -0.83$ V and $E_{pa}^1 = -0.15$ and $E_{pa}^2 = -0.62$ V. As can be seen in Fig. 10, the cyclic voltammograms of the complexes **1** and **2** in the presence of CT-DNA exhibited significant shifts in the anodic and cathodic peak potentials. In both cases, upon addition of CT-DNA to solutions of **1** and **2**, the cathodic current decreases and the anodic current increase, indicating strong interaction existing between these complexes and CT-DNA.

DNA cleavage activity :

Incubation of the complexes **1** and **2** with the pBR 322 DNA resulted in the cleavage of the DNA (Fig. 11). The cleavage of the DNA was confirmed by the appearance of the band when compared with the control DNA. At a concentration of even 25 μg of the complex **1**, it is resulted in the complete cleavage of the DNA whereas amount required to cleave DNA completely for complex **2** is much higher (~ 50 μg or higher). Thus, complex **1** has much higher DNA cleavage activity than complex **2** and behaves a potent DNA cleaving agent.

Modelling of [Cu(L)] with the dodecamer d(ACCGACGTCGGT)₂ :

Molecular modelling studies on the three modes of interaction of [Cu(L)] with DNA has been performed by placing the complex in the major groove, minor groove of the duplex DNA and the central part of the dodecamer. The output binding energy value of the [Cu(L)] was -223.91 kcal/mol. According to this docking experiment and energy values obtained from the docking, [Cu(L)] was found to be strongly interacted with DNA sequence

Fig. 10. Cyclic voltammograms of the Cu^{II} complexes **1** and **2** showing changes in peak position upon addition of CT-DNA.

Fig. 11. Concentration dependent cleavage of the pBR 322 DNA by **1** and **2**. Lane 1 shows the control DNA. Lanes 2–5 show DNA + complex (25, 50, 75 and 100 µg, respectively).

$d(\text{ACCGACGTCGGT})_2$ (Fig. 12). The decrease of the energy value for the $[\text{Cu}(\text{L})]$ association is due to substantial H-bond formation between the metal complex and DNA leading to internal binding (Fig. 12).

Fig. 12. Interaction of $[\text{Cu}(\text{L})]$ with the DNA duplex through H-bonding interactions.

Conclusion

This present work in which we have reported design, syntheses, structural characterization and DNA interaction studies with molecular modeling of a twisted square planar mononuclear Cu^{II} complex and a dinuclear square pyramidal Cu^{II} complex stems from our continued interest in defining and evaluating the key DNA-binding interactions of varied geometry copper(II) complexes of phenolate based ligands, which would ultimately help in

the design of newer drugs and develop useful DNA structure probes and new selective and efficient DNA recognition and cleaving agents. The CT-DNA binding constant for the complexes are 2.73×10^4 ($R = 0.996$ for five points) and 2.32×10^4 ($R = 0.99$ for five points) and the K_{sv} value for were found to be 2.67×10^4 ; ($R = 0.97$ for five points) and 1.83×10^4 ; ($R = 0.90$ for five points), indicating a strong affinity of the complexes to CT-DNA. It would be an opportunity to probe the DNA binding process itself and gain structural insight into the binding event. We aim at establishing the structural foundation for the design of new metal complexes, which possess more potent DNA binding affinities and DNA cleaving tendencies.

Supplementary data

CCDC 946621 contains the supplementary crystallographic data for **1**. These data can be obtained free of charge via <http://www.ccdc.cam.ac.uk/conts/retrieving.html>, or from the Cambridge Crystallographic Data Centre, 12 Union Road, Cambridge CB2 1EZ, UK; Fax : (+44) 1223-336-033; or E-mail: deposit@ccdc.cam.ac.uk.

Experimental

Materials and methods :

High purity salicylaldehyde (Alfa Aesar, UK), 1,3-diaminopropan-2-ol (Aldrich, UK), copper(II) chloride dihydrate (Merck, India), ammonium thiocyanate (Merck, India), triethylamine (Merck, India) and all other solvents were purchased from the respective concerns and used as received. The calf thymus CT-DNA and ethidium bromide (EB) were obtained from Sigma. Commercially available solvents were used as received without further purification.

Physical measurements :

Elemental analyses (carbon, hydrogen and nitrogen) were performed on a Perkin-Elmer 2400 CHNS/O elemental analyzer. IR spectra (KBr discs, $4000\text{--}300\text{ cm}^{-1}$) were recorded using a Perkin-Elmer FT-IR model RX1 spectrometer. Ground-state absorption and steady-state fluorescence measurements were made with a Jasco model V-530 UV-Vis spectrophotometer and Hitachi model F-4010 spectrofluorimeter, respectively. The EPR spectrum

was recorded on a Bruker EMX-X band spectrometer. Electrochemical studies were carried out with a VersaStat-PotentialStatII cyclic voltammeter using saturated calomel electrode (SCE) as the reference electrode in a three-electrode system. The ^1H NMR spectra were recorded on a Bruker AC300 spectrometer. Electrospray ionization (ESI) mass spectra were recorded using a Waters micro Q-TOF mass spectrometer.

Preparation of **L** and Cu^{II} complexes **1-2** :

The Schiff base **L** and copper complexes were prepared following a reported method²¹. The details are given below :

Salisaldehyde (0.244 g, 2 mmol) was heated under reflux with 1,3-diaminopropan-2-ol (0.086 g, 1 mmol) in 30 ml dehydrated alcohol. After 10 h the reaction solution was evaporated under reduced pressure to yield a gummy mass, which was dried under vacuum and stored over CaCl_2 for subsequent use. Yield 0.288 g (87.2%). Anal. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{18}\text{N}_2\text{O}_3$ (**L**) : C, 68.48; H, 6.08; N, 9.39. Found : C, 68.40; H, 6.02; N, 9.35; ^1H NMR (CDCl_3) δ : 3.68 (2H, dd, J 12.4, 6.8 Hz), 3.84 (2H, dd, J 12.4, 4.0 Hz), 4.23–4.25 (1H, m), 6.88 (2H, t, J 7.2 Hz), 6.96 (2H, d, J 8.4 Hz), 7.25 (2H, dd, J 7.6, 1.6 Hz), 7.32 (2H, td, J 8.8, 1.6 Hz), 8.36 (2H, s) ppm; ^{13}C NMR δ : 62.9, 70.2, 117.0, 118.5, 118.6, 131.5, 132.5, 161.1, 167.3 ppm; IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) : 1634, 1611 ($\nu_{\text{C}=\text{N}}$), 3412 (ν_{OH}); UV-Vis (λ_{max} , nm) : ~221, 256, 316, 403 nm.

Complex **1** was synthesized by dropwise addition of methanolic solution (5 cm^3) of **L** (0.298 g, 1 mmol) into a solution of $\text{CuCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (0.170 g, 1 mmol) in the same solvent (10 cm^3). The deep green solution was filtered and the supernatant liquid was kept in air for slow evaporation. The single crystals suitable for X-ray diffraction studies were obtained in 4–6 days. Yield 0.117 g (74% based on metal salt). Anal. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{17}\text{H}_{16}\text{N}_2\text{O}_3\text{Cu}$ (**1**) : C, 58.52; H, 5.69; N, 7.18. Found : C, 58.45; H, 5.61; N, 7.11%; IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) : 1627, 1601 ($\nu_{\text{C}=\text{N}}$), 3202 (ν_{OH}); UV-Vis (λ_{max} , nm) : 248, 267, 370, 603 nm.

Complex **2** was synthesized by dropwise addition of methanolic solution (10 cm^3) of **L** (0.298 g, 1 mmol) into a stirred methanolic solution (10 cm^3) of $\text{CuCl}_2 \cdot 2\text{H}_2\text{O}$ (0.340 g, 2 mmol) and triethylamine was added dropwise to the reaction mixture to maintain the solution pH 9.

The organic base was used to deprotonated the aliphatic-OH group. After that, methanolic solution (5 cm^3) of NH_4NCS (0.076 g, 1 mmol) was added to above solution and kept on magnetic stirrer for another 20 min. The dark brown clear solution was filtered and the supernatant liquid was kept in air for slow evaporation. After 7–10 days brown coloured crystalline compound appeared. Yield 0.276 g (75% based on metal salt). Anal. Calcd. for $\text{C}_{18}\text{H}_{19}\text{N}_3\text{O}_5\text{SCu}_2$ (**1**) : C, 41.86; H, 3.71; N, 8.14. Found : C, 41.79; H, 3.68; N, 8.18%; IR (KBr, cm^{-1}) : 3450 (ν_{OH}), 1625, 1603 ($\nu_{\text{C}=\text{N}}$), 2079 (ν_{NCS}), 852 ($\nu_{\text{O-C}}$); UV-Vis (λ_{max} , nm) : 233, 271, 357, 615.

Viscosity measurements :

For viscosity studies sonicated DNA of (280 ± 40 base pairs) was used. The viscosity of the DNA-metal complexes were determined by measuring the time needed to flow through a Cannon-Manning semi micro size 75 capillary viscometer (Cannon Instruments Company, State College, PA, USA) that was submerged in a thermostated water bath ($20 \pm 1\text{ }^\circ\text{C}$). Small volumes of the solution of **1** and **2** were added to sonicated CT-DNA solution placed in the viscometer. Mixing was effected by slowly bubbling dry nitrogen gas. Flow times were measured in triplicate to an accuracy of ± 0.01 s with an electronic stopwatch Casio Model HS-30W (Casio Computer Co. Ltd., Tokyo, Japan). Relative viscosities for DNA either in the presence or absence of **1** and **2** were calculated from the relation,

$$\eta'_{\text{sp}}/\eta_{\text{sp}} = \{(t_{\text{complex}} - t_0)/t_0\}/\{(t_{\text{control}} - t_0)/t_0\} \quad (1)$$

where, η'_{sp} and η_{sp} are specific viscosities of the **Cu**-DNA adducts, and the DNA, respectively; t_{complex} , t_{control} and t_0 are the average flow times for the **Cu**-DNA adducts, free DNA and buffer, respectively.

X-Ray diffraction study :

Single crystal data of **1** were collected on a Bruker AXS KAPPA APEX II diffractometer using $\text{Mo-K}\alpha$ radiation ($\lambda = 0.71073\text{ \AA}$) at 150(2) K. Systematically absent reflections led to the identification of space groups $P-1$ for **1**. Of the 10349 total reflections for the complex, 2636 with $[I > 2\sigma(I)]$ were used for structure solutions. The structures were solved by direct methods, and the structure solution and refinement were based on $|F^2|$. All non-hydrogen atoms were refined with anisotropic displacement parameters whereas hydrogen atoms were

placed in calculated positions when possible and given isotropic U values 1.2 times that of the atom to which they are bonded. The final differences Fourier map showed the maximum and minimum peak heights at 1.49 and $-0.34 \text{ e.}\text{\AA}^{-3}$ for **1** with no chemical significance. All calculations were carried out using SHELXL-2000²².

DNA cleavage studies :

Cleavage of supercoiled pBR 322 DNA by **1** and **2** were monitored by agarose gel electrophoresis technique. The complexes (25–100 μg) were incubated with pBR 322 DNA overnight at 37 °C. After incubation 2 μL of bromophenol blue dye was mixed with the sample and loaded carefully into the electrophoresis chamber wells along with the control DNA. TAE buffer was used as a running buffer and finally loaded on agarose gel and passed the constant 50 V of electricity for 30 min. Then the bands were observed in the gel containing EB under the gel documentation system and photographed to determine the extent of DNA cleavage and the results are compared with the control.

Molecular modelling studies :

The twelve base pairs sequence DNA d(ACCGACGTCGGT)₂ (PDB ID : 423D) duplex receptor was selected for molecular docking study. The 3D coordinates of the crystal structure of the DNA duplex receptor structure was downloaded from the Protein Data Bank (<http://www.rcsb.org/pdb/home.do>). Before docking, the DNA structure was stimulated and modified following the previously described methods²³. The structures of the free ligand and [Cu(L)] were constructed using ChemBioDraw Ultra 12.0. HEX 6.3 was used to setup and perform docking calculations between the metal complex and DNA sequence. The default parameters were used for performing docking.

Acknowledgement

B. Biswas gratefully acknowledges the financial support from the University Grants Commission, New Delhi, India (F. No. PSW-84/12-13(ERO) dated 05/02/2013). I acknowledge Dr. C. Malla Reddy for providing SCXRD studies. PPB thanks CSIR (New Delhi) for financial support.

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